

A proof of the Legendre's conjecture

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Abstract: The Legendre's conjecture states that there is a prime between every two pairs of consecutive squares of positive integers. In this paper, we prove this conjecture by comparing with an interesting sequence.

1. Introduction

The Legendre's conjecture is an open question about prime numbers [1, 2]. It is known as one of Edmund Landau's four "unattackable" problems [3] mentioned in 1912. The conjecture states [4] there is at least one prime between n^2 and $(n + 1)^2$ for any positive integers n . Anyone with a little basic mathematical knowledge can understand and check it. Unfortunately, despite making research progress^{5,6,7}, there's infinite numbers and no one has ever managed to prove or refute.

To describe the results, we make the following definition.

Active factor: The active factor of number n is the largest factor among all factors less than or equal to \sqrt{n} of n . A number has only one active factor. The active factor of prime number is 1, and the active factor of composite number is greater than 1. For example, 3 is the active factor of 15; 5 is the active factor of 35 and 55; 7 is the active factor of 105.

Consecutive Odd Number Sequence (CONS): The consecutive odd number sequence is a sequence consisting of adjacent positive odd numbers that follow each other in the order from smallest to largest. The difference between any predecessor-successor pair is 2. Its length is equal to the number of odd numbers in the sequence, and each odd number in CONS is called an item. For example, 13-15-17-19-21 and 91-93-95-97 are two CONS with lengths equal to 5 and 4 respectively.

Consecutive Active Factor Sequence (CAFS): The continuous active factor sequence is a sequence, which means that each number in CONS is replaced by its active factor. Its length is equal to the length of the original CONS, and its effective length is equal to the number of composite numbers in the original CONS. Each active factor in CAFS is called an item. For example, 3-1-5-3-1 is CAFS of 21-23-25-27-29 with lengths equal to 5, and its effective length is 3.

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Subsequence: Subsequence is the part left after sequentially removing the first or last item of a CONS or CAFS, thus it is also a CONS or CAFS. For example, 15-17-19 is CONS by removed 13, 23 and 21 of 13-15-17-19-21-23, and 3-1-5 is CAFS by removed the first 3 and last 1 of 3-1-5-3-1. Note that only the middle item cannot be removed, even if the relative position remains unchanged, such as 15-19-23 is not CONS by removed 13 and 17 of 13-15-17-19-21-23.

Number of Active Factors: The number of active factors k is the total number of item which factors including k in CAFS of S , represented by $S(k)$. For example, the CAFS of S is 3-1-5-9-7-11-3, and $S(3)=3$. The CAFS of G is 5-3-1-7-9-5, and $G(5)=2$.

2. Preliminaries

In the following, let T denote a CONS or subsequence of a CONS with length equal to n , where all odd numbers in T can be written as $m, m+2, m+4, m+6, \dots, m+2n-2$, and m and n are both positive odd numbers. S is a CAFS formed by T . Additionally, let G and H denote two different CAFSs with length equal to n .

Proposition 1. The difference between the length and the effective length of S is equal to the number of primes in T .

Proof. The length of S is the number of all numbers in T , and the effective length of S is the number of composite numbers in T , so the difference between the length and the effective length of S is equal to the number of primes number in T . \square

Proposition 2. Let k be a positive odd number and $k \geq n$, there is at most one number whose factors include k in T .

Proof. Suppose k is the factor of at least two numbers in T , and two of them are x and y ($x > y$). x and y can be expressed as $u * k$ and $v * k$ (u and v are positive odd numbers, and $u > v$), respectively. The difference between x and y is $(u - v) * k$. Because the difference between u and v is the multiple of 2, the minimum difference between x and y is $2 * k$. However, the difference between any two numbers in T is at most $2 * (n-1)$. Since $2 * (n-1) < 2 * k$, it is impossible for two or more factors in T to include k . Therefore, there is at most one number whose factors include k in T . \square

Proposition 3. Let k be a positive odd number and $k \leq n$, there is at least one number whose factors include k in T .

Proof. Let t denote the remainder of m divided by k . I.e., $m=q*k+t$ (q and t are integer and $q \geq 0, 0 \leq t \leq k-1$).

If $t = 0$, it is obvious that k is a factor of m .

If $0 < t \leq k-1$ and t is even number, then $t \geq 2$ and $m-t+2k < m-t+2n$, thus k is a factor of $m-t+2k$ that is in T .

If $0 < t \leq k-1$ and t is odd number, then $m-t+k < m-t+n$, thus k is a factor of $m-t+k$ that is in T .

Therefore, there is at least one number whose factors include k in T . \square

Proposition 4. There is only one number whose factors include n in T .

Proof. According to **Proposition 2**, it can be inferred there is at most one number whose factors include n in T . Additionally, there is at least one number whose factors include n in T according to **Proposition 3**. Therefore, there is only one number whose factors include n in T . \square

Proposition 5. Let k, r be two positive odd number, and numbers of items whose factors include k are r in T , then there is at least one number whose factors include $r*k$ in T .

Proof. Let $q*k$ be the smallest number whose factors include k in T , and q is a positive odd number, then k is a common factor of $q*k, (q+2)*k, (q+4)*k, \dots, (q+2r)*k$, all of which are in T .

$q-(q+2)-(q+4)-\dots-(q+2r)$ is a CONS with length equal to r . According to **Proposition 3**, there is at least one number whose factors include r , so among $q*k, (q+2)*k, (q+4)*k, \dots, (q+2r)*k$, there is at least one number whose factors include $r*k$.

Therefore, there is at least one number whose factors include $r*k$ in T . \square

Proposition 6. Let k, u , and v be three positive odd numbers. If k is a factor of u , and u is an active factor of v , then k is a factor of v .

Proof. Let $u=k*r$ and $v=u*q$, where r and q are positive odd numbers. So $v=k*r*q$, and k is a factor of v . \square

Proposition 7. Let k be a positive odd number and $k \geq n$, there is at most one number whose factors include k in G .

Proof. Suppose that there are two or more of numbers whose factors include k in G . According to **Proposition 6**, it can be inferred that there are two or more of numbers whose factors include k in the CONS that forms G ,

which contradicts **Proposition 4**. Therefore, there is at most one number whose factors include k in G . \square

According to **Proposition 7**, it can be inferred that there is at most one number whose factors include n in G and H . In addition, there will be no CAFS such as 3-5-3 or 7-3-1-5-3-5-7.

Proposition 8. Let a be a positive odd number. If there is only one number whose factors include a in the subsequence with length equal to a in H , and $G(a) > H(a)$, then:

- (i) there is only one number whose factors include a in the subsequence with length equal to a in G ;
- (ii) $G(a) = H(a) + 1$;
- (iii) $G(a) * a > n$;
- (iv) $(G(a) - 1) * a < n$.

Proof. (i) If there is no number whose factors include a in one subsequence with length equal to a in G , then the number of $G(a)$ is at most g . This contradicts $G(a) > H(a)$. Therefore, there is only one number whose factors include a in the subsequence with length equal to a in G .

(ii) Divide G and H into multiple independent subsequences with length equal to a , and the remaining subsequences with length equal to k are G_B in G and H_B in B ($0 < k < a$), respectively. The number of subsequences with length equal to a is g , and the number of $H(a)$ is at least g .

The number of active factors a in all subsequences with length equal to a in G is the same as that in all subsequences with length equal to a in H . According to **Proposition 6** and **Proposition 2**, there is at most one number whose factors include a in G_B and H_B respectively, thus there is one number whose factors include a in G_B and there is no whose factors include a in H_B . Therefore, $G(a) = H(a) + 1$.

(iii) $n = H(a) * a + k < H(a) * a + a$, so $G(a) * a = (H(a) + 1) * a = H(a) * a + a > n$, that is, $G(a) * a > n$.

(iv) $n - 1 = H(a) * a + k - 1 \geq H(a) * a$, that is, $(G(a) - 1) * a < n$. □

3. An interesting CAFS

Let T be a CONS consisting of all odd numbers between n^2 and $(n + 1)^2$ except n^2 and $(n + 1)^2$. S is a CAFS formed by T , and the lengths of T and S are both n .

Since the active factor of each number in T is less than or equal to $\sqrt{n^2}$, every item of S is less than or equal to n . Obviously, Legendre's conjecture can be described as:

the effective length of a CAFS in which each active factors is less than or equal to n is less than n .

Let's discuss an interesting CAFS L in which each active factors is less than or equal to n .

When $n = 5$, L is 5-3-1-1-3, and the effective length is 3.

When $n = 6$, L is 5-3-1-1-3-5, and the effective length is 4.

When $n = 7$, L is 7-5-3-1-1-3-5, and the effective length is 5.

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When $n = 12$, L is 11-9-7-5-3-1-1-3-5-7-9-11, and the effective length is 10.

When $n = 13$, L is 13-11-9-7-5-3-1-1-3-5-7-9-11, and the effective length is 11.

When n is an odd number, L is as follows:

n -...-15-13-11-9-7-5-3-1-1-3-5-7-9-11-13-15-...-($n-2$)

When n is an even number, L is as follows:

($n-1$)-...-15-13-11-9-7-5-3-1-1-3-5-7-9-11-13-15-...-($n-1$)

Proposition 9. Let k be a positive odd number and $1 < k \leq n$, there is only one number whose factors include k in the subsequence with length equal to k in L .

Proof. Let L_k be a subsequence with length equal to k in L , and L can be divided into two independent continuous odd sequences starting from 1, which are L_1 and L_2 .

When L_k only belongs to L_1 or L_2 , according to **Proposition 4**, There is only one number whose factors include k in L_k .

Let L_3 be a subsequence with length equal to $2 * k$ in L , and L_3 is $(2k-1)-(2k-3)-...-(k)-(k-2)-...-3-1-1-3...-(k-2)-(k)-...-(2k-3)-(2k-1)$. When L_k does not only belongs to L_1 or L_2 , L_k belongs to L_3 . Obviously,

there is only one number whose factors include k in any subsequence with length equal to k in L_3 , thus there is only one number whose factors include k in L_k .

Therefore, there is only one number whose factors include k in the subsequence with length equal to k in L . \square

Proposition 10. Let k be a positive odd number and $1 < k < n$, $L(k) + 1$ is an odd number greater than or equal to 3.

Proof. Each number in L appears twice except 1 and n , thus $L(k)$ is an even number greater than or equal to 2, and $L(k) + 1$ is an odd number greater than or equal to 3. \square

4. Proof of conjecture

Theorem 1. Let T be a CONS consisting of all odd numbers between n^2 and $(n + 1)^2$ except n^2 and $(n + 1)^2$, and S is a CAFS formed by T , then the effective length of S is less than or equal to $n - 2$.

Proof. Suppose the effective length of S is greater than $n - 2$.

Recall that the CAFS L with length equal to $n - 2$ is given by **Proposition 9**. The lengths of L and S are both n , and their active factors are both less than or equal to n . The effective length of S is greater than that of L , which indicates that there is at least one active factor a such that $S(a) > L(a)$.

According to **Proposition 5**, It can be inferred that numbers of items whose factors include a are $S(a)$ in T .

According to **Proposition 6**, there is at least one number whose factors include $S(a) * a$ in T . Thus, there is a positive odd number b such that $n^2 < S(a) * a * b < (n + 1)^2$.

According to **Proposition 8**, it can be inferred that $S(a) * a > n$, $S(a) = L(a) + 1$ and $(S(a) - 1) * a < n$.

Since $S(a) * a > n \geq n + 1$ and $S(a) * a * b < (n + 1)^2$, It can be inferred that $b \leq n$.

Since $(S(a) - 1) * a < n$ and $S(a) * a * b > n^2$, It can be inferred that $b > (S(a) - 2) * a$.

Hence, $a \leq (S(a) - 2) * a < b \leq n < S(a) * a$. According to **Proposition 9**, $S(a)$ is an odd number greater than or equal to 3. Thus, a is not factor of the active factor of $S(a) * a * b$, otherwise, the active factor of $S(a) * a * b$ is either less than b or greater than n .

Therefore, the effective length of S is not greater than that of L , and the effective length of S is less than or equal to $n - 2$. \square

According **theorem 1**, it can be inferred that there is at least one prime between n^2 and $(n + 1)^2$

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